

STUDIES IN TERPENES. PART VII. A CONTRIBUTION TO THE CHEMISTRY OF TERPINEOL DEHYDRATION

BY JAMES VERGHESE

Earlier researches on the transformations of terpineol with fused potassium hydrogen sulphate, aq. oxalic acid, sulphuric-acetic acid mixture and γ -alumina have been repeated, and in the reaction mixtures, α -terpinene, limonene and saturates have been quantitatively estimated.

Reactions of terpineol, catalysed by iodine and boric acid, have been examined, and iodine has been found to be an excellent and quick agent for dehydrating terpineol.

For eliminating α -terpinene in terpene mixtures, warming with maleic anhydride is shown to be a better route than agitating with cold Beckmann's chromic acid mixture.

Bromination of terpinolene by Baeyer's technique has been improved, the essential change being the precipitation of the tetrabromide by addition of cold methanol. This modification avoids the formation of oily products.

No clean-cut elimination path for terpineol is revealed excepting in dehydrations with potassium hydrogen sulphate and alumina, wherein *dl*-limonene and terpinolene respectively are obtained as major reaction products. In all other cases, there result monocyclics containing α -terpinene, terpinolene, limonene and saturates including *p*-cymene, in varying proportions.

A mechanism is proposed to account for the reaction products and to explain how terpineol can furnish both terpinolene and limonene with equal facility.

Much work has been done on the dehydration of terpineol. Wallach (*Annalen*, 1893, 275, 103) reported that refluxing terpineol for one hour with fused potassium hydrogen sulphate afforded chiefly dipentene (cf. Flawitsky, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1956; Kremers, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1909, I, 80, 21; Richter and Wolff, *Ber.*, 1930, 63B, 1721), while refluxing for half-hour with aq. oxalic acid gave essentially terpinolene (cf. Baeyer, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 436; Roberts and Day, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1226). On increasing the reaction period with aq. oxalic acid to five hours, the alcohol yielded a considerable quantity of α -terpinene, some terpinolene and 1:4-cineole (cf. Goodway and West, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 702). A more drastic treatment with sulphuric-acetic acid mixture resulted mostly in *p*-cymene and a little α -terpinene (Wallach, *loc. cit.*). It was concluded that the nature of the final products depended on three factors, viz., dehydrating medium, temperature and reaction period.

Further examination of the action of aq. oxalic acid on terpineol has been carried out by other investigators. Dupont *et al.* (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1933, 53, 393; cf. Booker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1453) found that the crude α -terpinene, separated from the reaction mixture, contained 1:4-cineole (40%), and appreciable amounts of dipentene, terpinolene and α -terpinene. Cineole was determined by complexing with hydroferrocyanic acid, and the other constituents by the Raman spectra (cf. Angus, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1938, 8A, 538). On the other hand, Lacrue (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1942, II, 1795) found that the yield of hydrocarbons increased with longer periods of refluxing and higher oxalic acid concentrations. 1:4-Cineole was estimated by the method of Dupont *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), limonene by interaction with aq. mercuric acetate (cf. Balbiano, *Ber.*, 1915, 48, 394), and terpinolene by deacetonisation under pressure. Recently Royals ("Advanced Organic Chemistry", Prentice-Hall, Inc., Englewood Cliffs, N. J., 1956, p. 231) indicated that 50% and 10% oxalic acid treatment of terpineol furnished α -terpinene (34%) and 1:4- and 1:8-cineoles (26%) respectively.

Finally, alumina can eliminate water from terpineol. When passed over ordinary alumina at 310-20°, terpineol gave mainly terpinolene (Maible, *J. usines gaz.*, 1923, 47, 370; cf. Dupont *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Other products, recognised in alumina dehydrations, are dipentene, α - and γ -terpinenes (Marot, *Bull. Inst. Pin.*, 1933, 38, 61) and *p*-cymene (Sondhi *et al.*, this *Journal*, *Ind. & News Ed.*, 1947, 10, 28).

In a recent publication, the reaction of terpineol, using the more active γ -alumina, has been reported (Santhanam and Yeddanapalli, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, 18, 328). Thus the catalysate obtained at 400° included α -terpinene (9%), terpinolene (23%) and *p*-cymene (8%), these percentages being calculated from the yield of the nitrosite, tetrabromide and terephthalic acid respectively. No other hydrocarbons could be detected in the reaction mixture.

The object of the present study is two-fold: (1) to re-investigate the transformations of terpineol (*a*) in the liquid phase, using fused potassium hydrogen sulphate, aq. oxalic acid and sulphuric-acetic acid mixture, and (*b*) in the vapour phase, over γ -alumina, and (2) to examine the behaviour of terpineol towards iodine and boric acid, with a view to clarifying and estimating the reaction products, and to propose a reaction mechanism.

EXPERIMENTAL

A technical grade terpineol was rectified, and the portion with b.p. 217.5-18.5°/760 mm, 148-49°/100 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4780 and d_{20}^{25} 0.9314 was used in these studies.

Oxalic, acetic, sulphuric and boric acids were of analytical grade, and potassium hydrogen sulphate, iodine and maleic anhydride were of chemically pure grade.

γ -Alumina catalyst was prepared by precipitation of the hydroxide from an aq. solution of potassium aluminate as recommended by Eischens and Selwood (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 2271).

The catalytic unit employed in the gas phase reaction was of the conventional type described earlier (Verghese and Kuriacose, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, 18, 364).

Reaction.—In general, the liquid phase reactions were carried out by heating terpineol under reflux with the dehydrating agent in question, except for iodine and boric acid reactions; in these cases, the reactants were subjected to slow distillation using a short Quickfit fractionating column. Reaction products were purified by steam distillation, dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and analysed.

The gas phase reaction was conducted at 400°, and at a liquid hourly space velocity, *i.e.*, the volume in c.c. of terpineol passed per c.c. of γ -alumina, (LHSV), of 0.34, and collecting the catalysate in a cooled receiver. The organic layer was separated, dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and analysed.

Analysis.—Estimation of α -terpinene was made by maleic anhydride addition (Verghese and Samson, *ibid.*, 1959, 18, 410), limonene by complexing with mercuric acetate (Lacrué, *loc. cit.*), and saturates by agitating with cold 80% sulphuric acid (Verghese *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1953, 12, 112).

Identification of α -terpinene was via the maleic anhydride adduct, m.p. and mixed m.p. 64-65° (cf. Ipatieff and Pines, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1945, **67**, 1227), limonene by conversion to terpin hydrate, m.p. and mixed m.p. 118° (Bhushan *et al.*, this *Journal, Ind. & News Ed.*, 1944, **7**, 62), and *p*-cymene in all samples of the saturates by oxidation to terephthalic acid (Leo *et al.*, *Curr. Sci.*, 1953, **22**, 112), and further conversion into dimethyl ester, m.p. and mixed m.p. 140-41° (Huntress and Mulliken, "Identification of Pure Organic Compounds, Order I", Chapman & Hall Ltd., Lond., 1946, p. 178) and into nitro derivative, m.p. and mixed m.p. 269° (Lange and Teranish, *J. Chem. Ed.*, 1955, **32**, 40). Terpinolene was recognised by the preparation of the tetrabromide, m.p. and mixed m.p. 116°, utilising a modification of the method of Baeyer (*Ber.*, 1894, **27**, 436) thus: Chilled in ice-salt, a mixture of the oil (1g.), amyl alcohol (1g.) and ether (2g.), and bromine was added dropwise to coloration. Addition of cold methanol precipitated the tetrabromide. The crude product was thrice precipitated from chloroform with methanol. The general scheme of analysis is summarised below:

Results for the transformations of terpineol in the liquid and gas phases are presented in Table I.

TABLE I

Transformations of terpineol.

Expt. No.	Terpineol.	Dehydrating agent.	Temp.	Period.	Analysis of monocyclics.				Terpinolene.		
					% Yield.	B.P. (750 mm. n_D^{20})	α -Terpinene.	Limonene.		Saturated.	
1.	25 g.	Fused potassium hydrogen sulphate 50 g.	180-90*	1 hr.	80	173-87°	1.4758	15%	63%	5.0%	+
2.	40	Oxalic acid, 120 g. Water, 240 g.	105-10°	5 hrs.	81	173-89°	1.4780	34	20	8.5	+
3.	20	Oxalic acid, 20 g. Water, 40 g.	105-10°	$\frac{1}{2}$ hr.	34	175-90°	1.4717	17	43	..	+
4.	30	Sulphuric acid, 2 g. Water, 4 g. Acetic acid, 100 c.c.	95-100*	7 hrs.	11	173-80°	1.4724	3	Traces	48	..
5.	40	Few crystals of iodine	Distilled	1 hr.	70	173-84°	1.4727	44	33	13	+
6.	25	Boric acid, 10 g.	Distilled	2 hrs.	76	173-89°	1.4747	42	29	..	+
7.	19.5	γ -Alumina, 15.15 g.	400° (LHSV, 0.34)	(LHSV, 0.34)	83	173-89°	1.4775	15	9	10	+

* Bath temperature.

Column 2 records the amount of terpineol used, and column 3, the dehydrating medium. Temperature and reaction periods are shown in columns 4 and 5 respectively. Yields of monocyclics on the weight of terpineol used and their physical characteristics are recorded in columns 6 to 8. The next three columns record the respective percentages of α -terpinene, limonene and saturates on the weight of the monocyclics; the + sign under the column headed terpinolene indicates the recognition of this hydrocarbon by tetrabromide preparation.

DISCUSSION

With fused potassium hydrogen sulphate, terpineol afforded 80% monocyclics. Dipentene constituted 63% of the monocyclics. Specificity claimed for this material to change terpineol completely to dipentene is untenable. There was the simultaneous formation of 15% α -terpinene, 5% saturates including *p*-cymene, and terpinolene. By difference, terpinolene should not exceed 17%. This assessment does not take into account the possible presence of γ -terpinene, *p*-menthene and *p*-menthane as reaction products. Richter and Wolff (*loc. cit.*) isolated by rigorous fractionation of crude dipentene, obtained by dehydration of terpineol with fused potassium hydrogen sulphate, about 12% of a cut, b.p. 71°/15 mm, which furnished the tetrabromide, m.p. 116°, corresponding to that of terpinolene. This observation is now confirmed by a different technique; the percentage of terpinolene, although approximate, agrees fairly well with that arrived at by earlier investigators. Attention may be drawn to the fact that if potassium hydrogen sulphate is not fused properly, an increase in the α -terpinene content is noticed at the expense of dipentene.

Five hours' refluxing of terpineol with aq. oxalic acid (Expt. 2) yielded 81% monocyclics; this contained 34% α -terpinene, 20% limonene, 8.5% saturates and terpinolene. Although Wallach (*loc. cit.*) reported extensive conversion to α -terpinene on the basis of the nitrosite yield, the maleic anhydride addition technique revealed the α -terpinene content to be 34% (cf. Royals, *loc. cit.*). Other novel findings are the identification of limonene and *p*-cymene as additional reaction products. On the other hand, half-hour's refluxing (Expt. 3), which is a standard method for terpinolene production, furnished only 34% monocyclics besides terpinolene; this included α -terpinene (17%), limonene (43%) and probably cineoles. Thus, even such a mild processing results in a mixture of *p*-menthadienes, difficult to be separated by fractionation (cf. Mosher, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2140). So, it is now suggested, that prior to tapping terpinolene, the monocyclics should be subjected to successive extractions with maleic anhydride, aq. mercuric acetate, hydroferrocyanic acid, and cold Beckmann's chromic acid mixture (cf. Richter and Wolff, *Ber.*, 1927, **60**, 477), in order to eliminate respectively α -terpinene, limonene, 1:4-cineole, and γ -terpinene, if any.

In contrast to the above experiments, with acetic-sulphuric acid mixture (Expt. 4), a sharp fall in monocyclics is observed (yield, 11%). As has been indicated by Wallach (*loc. cit.*), negligible quantity of α -terpinene (3%) and a high proportion of saturates (48%), including *p*-cymene, are found in the reaction mixture. From the refractive index of the saturates, n_D^{20} 1.4839, it is to be inferred that *p*-menthane is also present in the oil, but due to the limited quantity of the material, no attempt has been made to isolate this hydrocarbon. The presence of traces of limonene could be recognised by the formation of a very small amount of the mercuric acetate complex.

Findings with iodine (cf. Hibert, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **37**, 1748) and boric acid (cf. Bradenberg and Galt, *ibid.*, 1950, **72**, 3275; O'Connor and Nace, *ibid.*, 1955, **77**, 1578) are really

interesting. The technique of dehydration is simple, *i.e.*, slow distillation of terpineol with the catalyst. Without taking into account the pot residues, conversions to monocyclics with iodine and boric acid amounted to 70% and 76% respectively. In both cases, α -terpinene, limonene and terpinolene were identified as reaction products. With iodine, the dehydration was accompanied by *p*-cymene formation, and only a meagre yield of terpinolene (>10%) was obtained. Of the two catalysts, iodine seems to be the quicker and better for dehydrating terpineol.

Lastly, the gas phase reaction of terpineol over γ -alumina afforded α -terpinene, terpinolene, limonene and *p*-cymene. Santhanam and Yeddanapalli (*loc. cit.*), on the basis of the nitrosite yield, roughly calculated the α -terpinene content to be 9%, but now, by maleic anhydride addition, this conjugated diene is shown to amount to 15%. Further, the decomposition of α -terpinene by agitation with cold Beckmann's chromic acid mixture is tedious and erratic as the reagent is prone to attack other dienes (Baeyer, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 810; Guenther, "The Essential Oils", D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc., N.Y., 1952, Vol. II, p. 37; Verghese *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1957, 16A, 530; Henry and Paget, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 117, 1717; 1931, 26, 29). As is shown now, the same objective can be achieved in a better and cleaner way with maleic anhydride (*cf.* Gasgoine, *J. Proc. Soc., N. S. Wales*, 1941, 74, 353, 359). Percentages of α -terpinene-free oil arrived at by treatment with Beckmann's chromic acid mixture and maleic anhydride are 76 and 85 respectively. It is noteworthy that the presence of limonene has been established by hydroxylation to terpin hydrate, and estimated by mercuric acetate method (9%).

Calculating the same way as in the potassium hydrogen sulphate reaction, the vapour phase reaction affords about 66% terpinolene. Evidently then, the *exo* double bond in terpinolene resists migration even at 400° in presence of γ -alumina.

Reaction Mechanism.—Of great interest is the structure and orientation in elimination reactions of terpineol (I). Two primary products are available, *viz.*, terpinolene (V) and limonene (VI). Dehydration leading to terpinolene is in conformity with Satzvey's rule which states that the elimination proceeds in such a manner as to lose tertiary hydrogen in preference to that of primary or secondary (*Annalen*, 1875, 179, 300). This can be rationalised on the basis of hyperconjugative stabilisation of the transition state for the ejection of a proton from the intermediate carbonium ion (II), which can originate from terpineol by the action of hydrogen ion, iodine or alumina (Whit-

more, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 3274; *Chem. Eng. News*, 1948, **2**, 93; Wheland, "Advanced Organic Chemistry", 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons, Inc., London, 1951, p. 489; Hughes and Ingold, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1941, **37**, 657; Dhar *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 2093). Structure (III) represents most simply the transition state; the dotted lines indicate bonds partially formed or broken. Stabilisation of the incipient double bond by hyperconjugative mesomeric interaction with two methyl groups lowers the energy for expulsion of a proton, leading to terpinolene. On the other hand, the transition state represented by structure (IV) is stabilised by only one methyl group. Proton elimination from this, involving primary hydrogen, affords the least alkylated *p*-diene, limonene (cf. Ingold, "Structure & Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Cornell University Press, Ithaca, N. Y., 1953, p. 427; Brown *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 467; Brown, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, **22**, 439; Turner and Garner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 1424). How this reaction can compete with terpinolene production will be dealt with later.

There is no clear-cut elimination path except in reactions with potassium hydrogen sulphate and alumina; the major single product in these two reactions are 63% *dl*-limonene and 66% terpinolene respectively. In other cases, a mixture of *p*-menthadienes, viz., α -terpinene, terpinolene and limonene with saturates containing *p*-cymene, is obtained. The question naturally arises as to whether limonene or terpinolene is the primary reaction product from terpineol. This can only be answered by ascertaining whether limonene can rearrange to terpinolene and *vice versa* under the experimental conditions. Investigations are in progress in this laboratory to settle this point.

A common feature of almost all reactions under consideration is the formation of α -terpinene (VII) and *p*-cymene. α -Terpinene arises from C₉-ion (II) by a two-step process, viz., rearrangement by hydride ion shift and then expulsion of proton (Verghese *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1957, **16B**, 363), and this conjugated terpene is the most stable of the *p*-menthadienes to which all others converge (cf. Francesoni and Sernagiotto, *Gazzetta*, 1914, **44**, 456). As regards *p*-cymene, it can only originate as a consequence of hydrogen transfer reactions, fulfilling the prediction of Ipatieff and Pines (*loc. cit.*; Verghese, this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 155; Verghese *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

Lastly, we have to explain how the same organic entity (II) can yield terpinolene and limonene with equal facility. As has been pointed out before, the formation of terpinolene is to be expected on the basis of the maximum stabilisation of the incipient double bond of the transition state, and for expulsion of a proton only one hydrogen is available. Whereas for limonene formation, six hydrogens are available for a proton expulsion; this reaction can therefore compete with the energetically favoured ejection of a proton involving the tertiary hydrogen. What circumstances dictate the two modes of elimination cannot be said with certainty.

The author wishes to thank Prof. Dr. S. C. Devadatta, Head of the Dept. of Chemistry, Christian Medical College, Vellore, for interest in the work and for permission to publish the results. Also his thanks are due to Rev. Fr. Dr. Lourdu M. Yeddanapalli, S. J., Head of the Dept. of Chemistry, Loyola College, Madras, for permission to incorporate in this publication the results of the γ -alumina catalysed transformations of terpineol done in his laboratory.

Received December 12, 1959.